

Effect Of Ag And Na On Electrical Properties In LCSMO CMR Manganites

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Abstract.

Synthesis and characterization of colossal magnetoresistance (CMR) materials have been a subject of scientific research due to the unique transport, magnetotransport, and magnetic properties. The single phase polycrystalline $\text{La}_{0.7}\text{Ca}_{0.1}\text{Sr}_{0.1}\text{M}_{0.1}\text{MnO}_3$ (LCSMO) (M=Ag and Na) samples prepared using the nitrate route method. The temperature dependent electrical resistivity $\rho(T)$ of samples shows two transition peaks, a typical characteristics of Ag doped lanthanum based manganites while Na doped manganites exhibit one transition peak. In the high temperature range, the VRH model is found to simulate the resistivity behavior marginally better as compared to the small polaron model. The anomalous low temperature behavior is explained in terms of a model which combines electron-electron scattering and weak localization. The study of magneto transport behavior in both samples revealed enhanced negative MR of about 55 % in the low temperature range due to the spin polarized tunneling across the grain boundaries. Significant MR at room temperature can be exploited for magnetic sensing applications (1, 2).

Keywords: Nano-crystalline manganites, colossal magneto resistivity, metal to insulator transition, broad magnetoresistance, Weak localization.

References:

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